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Blue Humanities and Children’s Literature: The Praxis of Postcoloniality in the Disney Movies Moana & Pocahontas

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Abstract:

Blue humanities examine how oceans and other bodies of water are portrayed and represented in literary texts, exploring their cultural, social and political significance. It re-examines literary texts through a “blue-lens” thereby garnering new ways of narrative interpretations.

Children’s literature mitigates the concept of theoretical analysis in myriad ways. The idea of the sea as a dark and mysterious force is often undermined through narratives of the sea in an effort to annihilate the negative emotions of fear and fury associated with it. Literatures of the world have often treated the dread of death by water and the untamed furies of the majestic waves as themes of intimidating significance.

Contrary to these confounding notions that are rampant through the erudite academia, Disney movies such as Moana and Pocahontas portray a more humanistic picture of the sea as a living,

pulsating entity, that reaches out and talks to children. The proposed paper would attempt to analyze how Children's literature in general and Disney movies in specific etch new ways of comprehending oceans as material and social entities that serve as a dynamic metaphor of meaning formation. While Children's literature unfurls a narrative propaganda of its own, Disney movies coalesces concepts of environmental post-humanism with post-colonialism and decoloniality thereby making oceans the milieu of trans-disciplinary interactions as well as the narrative force behind its myriad discourses.

Keywords: Blue humanities, children's literature, Disney movies, narrative propaganda, trans-disciplinary interactions.

“An ocean is perpetually in mutation and always exceeding its geographic boundaries...Put two ships on the open sea, without wind and tide, and at last they will come together.”

(Jules Verne, 1871)

The deep blue sea beckons into its mysterious embrace seekers and voyagers alike, some in search of the farthest shores away from home and hearth while others thirsting for a route back home, urged on by the wail of lonely fog horns in some far and distant land. The lovers of the majestic blue element are called the Thalassophiles and they unconsciously reclaim a most vulnerable space for themselves over the ebb and flow of time. Oceans and its magical representations find a unique place in literatures of the world; Disney movies play a significant part in artistically recreating textual narratives into visual experiences that often manipulate fallacious undercurrents of meanings into its contours.

Moana and Pocahontas are two such movies that celebrate the oceanic metaphor through complex relationships of humans and the ocean with the aesthetics of cultural knowledge. The digressions of hegemony in visual narratives such as the ones mentioned above become passive as it emphatically over-rules the intended matrix of colonial discourses thereby nullifying its very attempt at the creation of cultural trope.

Moana, the 2016 Disney movie explores how an indigenous Pacific Oceanic tribe is driven by the need to find a new home and thereby, once again, taking up the role of sea-voyagers. Thus, for the first time in many decades, the daughter of the Chieftain, Moana, sets out into the open seas in search of a new paradise. Disney becomes the vehicle that transmits the narrative across the oceans. The intricate relationship between blue humanities and indigenous folklore is well stated in an article published in the special issue of the journal *World Literature and the Blue Humanities*.

It says,

“A key element in creating a global and multicultural blue humanities scholarship lies in listening to, and engaging with, those whose stories have been ignored.” (Smith & Steve 2020)

The name “Moana” owes its origins to the ancient Polynesian word that literally signifies the “sea beyond the reef, ocean” (Ross, Pawley, and Osmond 2007, 94). The main plot of the movie draws heavily from a story based on Polynesian and Tongan culture, which is something that has rarely been attempted within Hollywood. Disney sets the stage for an ancient culture, the Polynesian Culture, to depict the indigenous lives of the earliest sea farers long before the island’s first instances of Colonization by the “West”. The movie revolves around the Pacific people who enacted their own form of possession by staking a claim on how their collective story would be told by the media giant, Disney.

The very name “Moana”, signifies a linguistic cue that points towards myriad Polynesian languages spoken across the Pacific belt and is indicative of the infinite great voyages made by early inhabitants of these ancient islands who thirsted to explore “beyond the reefs” of their island shores. A clan of pioneering Austronesian-speaking migrants began their quest for new land forms some four or five thousand years ago. They voyaged across the West and journeyed into the Far East of the Pacific. These voyages involved multiple generations of men who excelled at the skilled craftsmanship of great sea-faring vessels. For these thalassophiles, the ocean was never a restrictive barrier but a watery highway that catalyzed cultural commutations and communications. The Disney movie Moana then takes us to the pre-colonial era whence displacement of communities was mobilized due to social and cultural deficits. The movie begins with a lilting Polynesian music and scintillating drum roll that transcends the viewers into an ethereal paradise of infinite beauty, bountiful nature and communal harmony. The Disney theme song that plays up the native culture itself seems to be a manipulative attempt at reclaiming decoloniality as its principal objective of discourse. The expositional story of the Mythology behind the Cultural fabric is done entirely in indigenous Polynesian style. The beliefs and rituals associated with the Polynesians encompass a Pantheon of gods to address the different facets of life. The movie introduces Demigods (Half Human and Half God) that manifest themselves as gallant sentinels of the islands thereby playing the role of cultural icons. The extensive display of stories on the Maui's body firmly establishes a multi-racial heritage, and his prominent tattoos, serve in the film as visual symbols of a somewhat generic “Polynesian” identity. (Baker and Marshall 2018)

At the beginning of the movie, the waves of the ocean teases the young Moana, as an indulging mother or grandmother, playfully beckoning the innocent child to the loving arms of its beautiful fluidity. Baby Moana experiences this magnetic pull towards the emerald green waters

of her island home right from her infancy. The infant now infatuated with the ocean is presented with the “Heart of Te Fiti”, thus making her the “chosen one”. But the little girl drops the heart into the depths of the ocean and returns to the protective arms of her parents. The myth unfurls that the relic was initially stolen from the Island’s heart by the Demigod Maui so that humans would gain power over all creation thereby making them indispensable in life. As baby Mauna grows up into a young maiden, the ocean persuades her to restore balance to the world by taking the “heart” back to Te Fiti. But Moana’s father who also happens to be the Island Chief forbids his young daughter from entering the waters, claiming it to be far too dangerous for the young and inexperienced lass. Moana unwittingly accepts her fate and rests her ambitions of crossing the reefs if only to appease her parents’ anxieties and the community’s expectations from her as the next Chief of the Island of Motunui. The archetype of the wise grandmother is well played out through Moana’s own grand-dame who entreats her to follow her dreams and leave the Island because it is what her heart truly desires. The days before Moana’s departure from the island is indeed filled with a great and momentous change in the destiny of the islanders who are distressed by diseased crops that fail to bear fruit. They are thereby haunted by the fears of an ancient curse that befalls the people who do not respect the earth that gives them sustenance. As food becomes scarce and crops fail to feed the community, the people are driven to search for newer lands that would provide them with sustenance. Disney pipes in with a scintillating song that once celebrated the voyager’s quest for unknown lands. The lines of the song go...

Aue, aue

We set a course to find

A brand new island everywhere we roam

Aue, aue

We keep our island in our mind

And when it's time to find home

We know the way

It is here that Disney plays its trump card of manipulating cultural discourses as a tool to justify Colonialism. The craftiness with which colonialism is narrated as an inevitable social necessity and not as a hegemonic weapon subtly foregrounds the connotative undertones that come into play in Disney's seemingly innocent screen narratives.

Moana's grandmother leads her to a cave where shrouded in the mysteries of time are found very large Polynesian voyaging ships, waiting for another lift of the tide and yet another gust of wind to fill the sails anew. The granddame tells her granddaughter that she must awaken the people of Motunui from their dormant existence on the island and remind them of their ancient identity as voyagers of the great oceans. Moana finally embarks on her quest on the night her grandmother passes away after yet another tiff with her father but sure of her mother's blessings and her grandmother's promise of accompanying her through her adventures in spirit. The granddame soon leaves her physical entity and mingles with the ocean's soul as a Ray fish that gracefully mingles with the waves in the sea, sharing secrets with the wind and the stars.

The chronicles of the earliest travelers in the eighteenth century related stories of Western voyagers who journeyed through the region via written and visual narratives. In an article titled Learning an Inclusive Blue Humanities: Oceania and Academia through the Lens of Cinema, James L. Smith and Steve Mentz states how after arriving in Tahiti in 1768, for instance, French explorer Louis-Antoine de Bougainville wrote that the experience was like being "transported into the garden of Eden" (1772, 228). An eco-critical reading of the film would then garner how life comes to a standstill once the heart of Te Fiti is stolen. The pacific paradise trope becomes a place of deadly

storms where life becomes impossible. Environmental post-humanism would deem it as stolen heart of Te Fiti as human exploitation of nature in terms of depletion of resources such as fish and food on the island. And Moana's attempts at restoration of Te Fiti's heart would symbolically imply a slow but sure return to environmental sustainability.

The internal inconsistencies and problematics of the patterns through which Disney brings to the tinsel screen these hegemonic power structures are quite debatable, and not entirely lost on erudite scholarship. As Smith and Steve Mentez states,

“Embracing post-colonial notions of authority, motion, intellectual inquiry, space, and place highlights the ambivalent nature of the process. The oceans of the world are places that have served as vehicles of travel for colonial exploitation and human suffering, but they also tell a plurality of stories.” (Smith and Steve 2020)

The whole gamut of blue humanities and storytelling transfers knowledge in two ways. Firstly, as a quest narrative wherein voyagers move out of their territories in search of greener pastures like the one portrayed in the movie Moana and secondly, as resistance narratives wherein territories ward off colonial voyagers in an effort to incubate one's own identity as in land, language and culture thereby attempting to retain its pristine genealogy.

(Smith and Steve 2020)

The Disney movie Pocahontas that was produced in 1995 brings us to this second strand of oceanic narratology. It narrates the story of a Native American girl called Pocahontas, the daughter of the village chief. The movie showcases how a huge fleet of ships anchor on the shores beyond the densely forested island. The danger that the white man brings to the natives in terms of deforestation, mining, logging and pollution is starkly portrayed in contrast to the harmonious existence of indigenous tribes who communicate with the flora and fauna around them. As fate

would have it, Pocahontas falls in love with a white man called John Smith. Although they hail from entirely different circumstances, the two unite and make an effort to restore peace between the European settlers and the Native Americans. And the highly volatile milieu becomes the point of contention wherein a subtle bond of communication is established between the greedy colonizers and the unyielding Native. The portrayal of Pocahontas as a princess in a Native American tribe would indeed assist in changing the perception of young children, for being a princess would then mean to inculcate the character of a powerful, successful, loved, strong, special, beautiful and independent girl. Every woman is a princess, some aware of their strengths, while others still waiting to discover theirs.

Disney's efforts at creating stereotype out of cultural propaganda often becomes the basis of main stream ideologies across discourses. The Native Americans are often referred to as "savages" and movies that depict them in an inferior position to the white European settlers distort the common man's notions of cultural hegemony. There is an "Othering" that unwittingly occurs within the framework of Disney's screen narratives. It is indeed unfortunate that while majority of Disney's audience belongs to a very tender age, it infuses a misconstrued notion of cultural supremacy. John Smith, the European colonizer in the movie Pocahontas, speaks of the natives as "uncivilized people". This portrayal lacks the cultural sensitivity by Disney. John Smith in one of the scenes tells Pocahontas that their goal is to make the "savages" "civilized", thus emphatically reiterating Disney's ideology that white colonizers rule the earth in all might and glory while the Natives make up the dark savages, intended to be slaves to their white masters.

Agencies of hegemony, while remaining cautious to cultural significations within native discourses must also invariably endeavour to analyze the infinite possibilities within such a discourse. Thus, it is that Disney movies being the major stakeholder in the entertainment industry

must attempt at a reconciliation between the Indigenous cultures of the Native Americans as well as the dominant European settlers. (Baker 2016, 49) The transnational apparatus that Disney symbolizes must indeed offer useful case studies for thinking about strategic collaborative engagements between Native communities and global corporate enterprises like Disney in ways that can be productive for both parties. Visual narratives such as Disney movies should impart a creative vision that expounds the message of culture and identity as diadems of Oceanic narratives endorsing democratic existences in an era of environmental posthumanism.

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